

Entomological assessment and seroprevalence of zika virus in garoua, cameroon : implications for vector control and public health

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Abstract: The Zika virus is concerning due to its harmful effects on the body. In Garoua, Cameroon, a previous study revealed a seroprevalence of 4.8%. The transmission of the Zika virus is possible through *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes, although only *Aedes aegypti* was found in Garoua. To determine the prevalence of Zika and assess potential vectors, 100 blood samples were analyzed using a Zika NS1 combo IgG/IgM cassette kit. Mosquito larvae from potential vector species were collected in three zones of Garoua: Yelwa, Jamboutou, and Roumde. All positive containers were recorded using GPS. Larval stages were collected by inspecting several categories of containers (domestic, peri-domestic, and natural), and the positive breeding sites were geo-referenced. Infestation indices (house index, Breteau index, container index, and larval index) were calculated. No cases of Zika were detected, with a prevalence of 0% in Garoua. However, both potential vectors were found in the city. Breteau indices were 39.60% in Yelwa, 51.42% in Jamboutou, and 31.81% in Roumde, indicating a high risk of Zika transmission in Roumde. The absence of positive cases could be due to the small sample size, highlighting the need for large-scale studies with a larger sample size. It is also essential to conduct research during wet and dry periods to better understand vector behavior and the circulation of the Zika virus in Garoua.

Keywords: Zika, NS1, prevalence, Cameroon, assessment, *Aedes aegypti*, *Aedes albopictus*

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Accepted: 28 July, 2024; **Published:** 29 July, 2024

How to cite this article: Layiroi Ningue Gervais, Bouba Gake, Nukenine Elias Nchiwan (2024). Entomological assessment and seroprevalence of zika virus in garoua, cameroon : implications for vector control and public health. North American Academic Research, 7(7), 147-168. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13306984>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Viral pathologies and emerging arboviroses affect millions of people every year, and have become recurrent news items in our modern world. These pathologies account for around 17% of the global burden of disease attributable to non-communicable diseases and are responsible for more than 700,000 deaths every year according to the World Health Organization[1]. They follow one another with accelerating frequency, probably due to changes in our lifestyles, the adaptation of their vectors to new geographical areas as a result of global warming and the explosion in international transport/trade.

Recent events have been marked by the emergence of Dengue (DENV) [2], Chikungunya (CHIKV) [3], Yellow Fever (YFV) [4] and Zika (ZIKV) viruses. The Zika virus, first identified in Uganda in 1947 in the Zika forest [5] has caused worldwide concern [6]. There are several genotypes of Zika virus: an Asian genotype involved in numerous epidemics such as those on Pacific islands, the Caribbean South/central America and an African genotype [7]. In recent decades, it has been widely associated with massive epidemics in several regions of the world, leading the WHO to classify it as a global threat due to its adverse effects on health, particularly in newborns [8] and in adults. It is estimated that around 70% of the population of sub-Saharan Africa is exposed to the Zika virus [9] [10]. Cameroon, as a tropical country, has been affected by Zika virus with cases reported in several regions of the country [11]. ZIKV is transmitted mainly by mosquitoes of the *Aedes* genus: *Aedes aegypti* [12] and *Aedes albopictus* [13], two mosquitoes belonging to the *Stegomyia* subgenus. *Aedes aegypti* has colonized all regions of the world. *Aedes aegypti* is native to Africa, while *Aedes albopictus* originates from a forest in Southeast Asia. The latter are also vectors of several arboviruses such as Dengue fever [14], Chikungunya [15] and Yellow fever virus [16]. They are found in a wide range of environments in tropical African countries, notably sub-Saharan Africa in countries such as the Central African Republic, Gabon, Senegal, Nigeria [17] [18] [10] and Cameroon [19]. The latter, characterized by a tropical climate and possessing conditions conducive to mosquito vector breeding, is considered a potential focus for Zika virus transmission. A previous study carried out in Cameroon demonstrated the presence of both vectors in the southern regions of the country, but only *Aedes aegypti* was found in the city of Garoua [20]. In view of all the above, several questions arise: is the Zika virus still circulating in the city of Garoua? What vectors are present today, and what are the risks of Zika transmission by potential vectors? To address these concerns, our overall aim is to determine the prevalence of Zika in the city of Garoua and to carry out an assessment of the distribution of potential vectors in order to understand the associated factors and see the impact of their distribution on the circulation of the Zika virus.

To this end, our specific objectives are as follows:

- test for the presence of Zika virus antibodies and antigens
- combine socio-demographic factors to determine risk factors for virus transmission
- identify the vectors present in Garoua
- Correlate the distribution of potential vectors with virus circulation in Garoua.

In order to achieve these objectives, a number of hypotheses are put forward:

- The Zika virus is still circulating in Garoua
- The environment influences Zika prevalence
- Zika vectors are present in the city of Garoua
- Vector abundance increases Zika virus prevalence

Materials and methods

Type of study

This study is a descriptive, analytical cross-sectional study. It measures the frequency of Zika cases over a short period, and collects quantifiable data on the vectors that can be used to assess risk factors for the population.

Study site

The research work took place in the northern region of Cameroon, precisely in the town of Garoua (09° 18'N, 13° 25'E). Garoua is a cosmopolitan city with an estimated population of over 400,000. It is the most densely populated city in the northern region. It has a tropical Sudanese climate (annual rainfall and temperature of 950 mm and 28°C respectively), with a rainy season from April to October. Garoua, located in the Benoue department, comprises 03 districts: Garoua I, Garoua II, Garoua III. The city is typically sahelian, with recognizable modern residential blocks developed by local authorities in central areas and traditional architectural structures found in outlying indigenous areas [21]. As in many cities in Cameroon, Garoua has a number of areas where poor management of garbage cans and vegetation around houses has led to an increase in water catchment, thus encouraging the proliferation of mosquitoes carrying the Zika virus.

Study framework

The Regional Hospital of Garoua is a large hospital created in 1932, first as the hospital departmental of Benoue, then as the hospital provincial de Garoua until 2010. It is located in the heart of the city of Garoua, in the first district. It is a category 3 hospital and the 2nd level of the health pyramid. The Garoua regional hospital currently covers an area of 10 hectares, with 53 buildings.

The participants

Study population

The study involved blood donors at Garoua regional hospital among consenting patients.

Sample size

The minimum sample size was determined using the LORENTZ formula based on the prevalence of Zika in Garoua in 2017. This prevalence, noted P , was 4.8%, with a confidence level $t=1.96$ for a rate of 95%; d is the margin of error set at 5%. $Q = 1 - P$. The LORENTZ formula is as follows: $N = P*Q*t^2/d^2$ Where: N = sample size; P = prevalence of ZIKV in Garoua; Q = opposite event to P ($Q=1-P$); $t = 95\%$ confidence level ($t=1.96$); d = desired precision with error of 0.05 (5%). For $P = 4.8\%$, we obtain $N = 70$ So for our study, the minimum sample size is 70.

Selection criteria

▣ Inclusion criteria

Included in the study: All adults aged 18 and over, regardless of sex, who consented to undergo the various tests at GAROUA Regional Hospital.

▣ Exclusion criteria

Not included in the study: Anyone who refused to take part in the study, and those outside the required age range.

Recruitment procedures

Participants in our study were recruited in the following stages:

All eligible participants in our study were welcomed and informed about the purpose of the study, the importance of their participation, and their freedom to take part or not. They were also made aware of lifestyles conducive to ZIKV contamination and the preferred locations of potential vectors. Consenting participants were then asked to complete a questionnaire and sign an informed consent form. After obtaining their consent, a 4ml blood sample was taken.

Blood sample collection methodology

For all our manipulations and analyses, we used the following equipment:

- **biological:** whole blood and/or plasma or serum,
- **non-biological:** EDTA tube rack, eppendorf tubes, yellow tips, syringes, tourniquets, gangs, ZIKV TDR, cotton, alcohol, micropipette, pastor pipette, centrifuge, refrigerator.

After the patients had given their consent, 4 ml of blood was drawn intravenously using a needle, a vacutainer and an EDTA (Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid) tube containing the anticoagulant to collect the plasma. After collection, the blood samples were introduced into a centrifuge and centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 3 minutes. The resulting plasma was collected using a micropipette and the yellow tip in code-marked eppendorf tubes, then placed in an ADTA tube rack. The latter is then stored in a refrigerator at 4-8° C before being used for Zika diagnosis.

The test used for diagnosis is the Zika NS1 IgG/IgM combo rapid test cassette (whole blood/serum/plasma) is a rapid test that uses a combination of Zika IgM/IgG antibodies and Zika NS1 antigen-coated colored particles for the detection of Zika IgM/IgG antibodies and Zika NS1 antigens in human whole blood, serum or plasma.

Entomological survey

We carried out entomological surveys from July to August 2023 in the city of Garoua in order to explore the potential breeding grounds of mosquitoes that may be vectors of the Zika virus. We divided the town of Garoua into zones that included the surrounding neighbourhoods. Firstly, the ROUMDE zone (9°20'56.3"N, 13°24'39.1"E), which includes the Roumde district and the surrounding districts (Poumpouméré, Marouaré, Doualaré, etc.), followed by the JAMBOUTOU zone (9°18'30.4"N, 13°21'02.7"E) which includes Jamboutou, Canadi, Wouro labo... and finally the YELWA zone (9°18'14.3"N, 13°21'06.1"E) which includes Soeto, Kolere, foulbere... In order to assess these different vectors, we relied on immature stages, which are easy to collect. The larvae were surveyed on foot. This is a method that enables mosquito larvae to be collected in their development environment (breeding site). The larvae were collected at different stages of development (1, 2, 3, 4 and nymph). The different collection areas are shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 : Location of vector collection

Larvae sampling method

To collect the larvae, we used a metal ladle attached to a piece of wood, from which we quickly (10-15 ladle strokes) drew water containing the lava. We then introduced the larvae into small plastic containers and jars. We then placed the jars or containers containing the larvae in 50 cm³ mosquito rearing cages until the larvae were transformed and adult mosquitoes emerged, enabling us to continue the process. On each breeding cage, one or two cotton balls soaked in glucose are placed above the breeding cage to serve as food for the emerging adults [1].

Recording collection information

We used a GPS positioning system to locate and number the sampled breeding sites. We then recorded the characteristics of the site, including :

- Geographical location (GPS coordinates, name of study area)
- Type of shelter (domestic, peri-domestic, natural)
- Sun exposure
- Presence of vegetation (submerged, floating)
- Water characteristics (e.g. clear, dark)

Figure 2: Mosquito breeding cages

Depending on the nature, source and use of the water, positive containers have been classified into 03 main categories: domestic, peridomestic and natural. Domestic containers are sites filled by humans in the home, peridomestic containers are those outside the home or that have been discarded (tin cans, snail shells, cosmetic jars, old vehicle parts that can hold water) and natural containers are those filled by rainfall (tree leaves, stagnant water, rock holes...). Once the larvae have emerged, potential Zika vectors are isolated from other mosquito species, then identified and counted, after which the abundance of vectors is recorded in a specially-designed notebook.

Vector identification

Aedes aegypti and *Aedes albopictus* are small mosquitoes, around 5mm long, with white markings on their bodies and legs. Their abdomens are pointed and scaly, sometimes with silver metallic markings. However, the 02 mosquitoes differ in a few particular respects: *Aedes aegypti* is rather brown/dark with a lyre-shaped pattern on the

thorax, is diurnal, mainly between 9am and 1pm, and flies at a maximum height of 1.5m. *Aedes albopictus*, on the other hand, is generally black with a longitudinal white stripe on the thorax, and is generally nocturnal, although the female may extend her hunting period into the day. After identifying the various potential vectors, we pooled 05 mosquitoes and separated the *Aedes aegypti* from the *Aedes albopictus* at each collection site, placing them in EDTA tubes and marking them with a black marker to preserve them for future use.

Infestation indicators

The levels of *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* were expressed with standard indices based on immature stages, we calculated the following indices which are good indicators of the population's behavior towards mosquito vectors:

- **Dwelling or house index (HI):** percentage of houses in which at least one container containing *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* larvae was encountered, relative to the total number of houses visited.
- **Breteau index (IB):** number of positive cottages per hundred houses visited.
- **Container index (CI):** percentage of positive containers (larval breeding sites) among all containers in water.
- **Larval index:** abundance of larvae per house.

The three indices - the "house" or "dwelling" index (IM), the "container" index (IR) and the Breteau index (IB) - have been defined by the World Health Organization to assess the frequency of *Aedes aegypti* in a given locality. These three indices, regularly used in entomology to measure the risk of dengue transmission, can be applied to *Aedes albopictus* given their similar living conditions.

The house index (HI) is characterized by three levels of risk: low risk if $HI < 0.1\%$, medium risk if $0.1\% \leq HI \leq 5\%$ and high risk if $HI > 5\%$.

The risk of ZIKV transmission is unlikely if $IB < 5$, but very high if $IB > 50$. Some specialists consider that the risk of transmission increases when IB exceeds 20.

The IR indicates only the proportion of positive containers, and the IM the proportion of positive houses. The IB combines information on containers (IR) and houses (IM). It is now recognized that these indices are not correlated with vector population densities. For example, few positive containers can produce a large number of adults, so the RI will be low while the vector density will be high.

These indices were associated with building density. Three classes were considered: high building density corresponded to areas with an average of 60 houses per ha; medium building density with 30 houses per ha; and low building density was defined as areas with less than 20 houses per ha.

Ethical considerations

The research protocol was submitted to the regional ethics committee for human health research in the North. A training authorization was approved by the director of the Garoua regional hospital. The objectives, benefits and risks were clearly explained in French, or translated into the Foulbe language where patients did not understand, to all participants prior to their inclusion in the study. An individual informed consent form was read and signed by each participant. All ethical rules were respected during sampling, including respect for human beings and the confidentiality of patients' personal data.

Statistical data analysis

All blood sampling and vector sampling data will be analyzed, geo-referenced and imported into QGIS 3.16 mapping software for mapping and processing. All sites with information on the presence/absence of *Aedes aegypti* and *albopictus* will be mapped in the study area using the available latitude and longitude coordinates. Container type, presence/absence of vegetation around the container, water source and quality, presence/absence of larvae were chosen as independent variables and percentages were compared using Person's Chi-square, while the number of *Aedes aegypti* and *albopictus* larvae was defined as the dependent variable. They were expressed as mean and standard deviation and compared using ANOVA. We also used Graphpad prism software to determine relative risks, P-values and confidence intervals. Finally, the different zones studied will be compared according to the number of *Aedes albopictus* and *Aedes aegypti* larvae. In order to design a survey form, we will use SPHINX software, which enables us to create questionnaires, enter responses, process data quantitatively and analyze data qualitatively. All analyses will be carried out using StatGraphics software, which has extensive capabilities for ANOVA (to determine whether the difference between mean values is statistically significant), multivariate statistics, design of experiments (PEX), statistical process control (SPC)... These software packages have useful functions for a well-posed statistical study,

whether describing the characteristics of a population, comparing 02 groups of data or studying the correlation between 02 groups of data.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population

Table I presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the study population, broken down according to sex, marital status, profession, knowledge of the virus, area near habitat, knowledge of the vector, means of protection against vectors, type of container likely to harbor vectors, frequency of mosquito bites, time of bite, means of protection against vectors, origin of water used and/or consumed and recent travels. The table shows that the study population was made up of 65 men (65%) versus 35 women (35%), with an average age of 29.01. The study shows that the distribution of the study population by residential area is as follows: 42 (42%) in the Jamboutou zone, 32 (32%) in the Yelwa zone and 26 (26%) in the Rounde zone (26%). Regarding knowledge of the virus, 97 (97%) of the study population were unaware of the virus and 3% were aware of it. As for *Aedes* vectors, 74 (74%) said they knew them and 26 (26%) did not. As for the time of the bite, 56 (56%) said they were constantly bitten, especially at night, i.e. 54 (57.1%) people. As for their contact with the environment, 69 (69%) of them live near ponds, and 48 (48%) have cans and old tires in or near their homes. Among the participants, the most representative were 37 (37%) students and 25 (25%) administrative staff. For vector control, 58 (58%) of participants use mosquito nets and 42 (42%) use insecticides. As for drinking water sources, 60 (60%) of the study population use water from boreholes, 28 (28%) from pumps, 9 (9%) from wells and 3 (3%) from rivers. Of the participants, 45% had traveled recently, while 65% were in the city. In terms of out-of-town travel, 34 (34%) people in the study population said they had recently travelled, compared with 66 (66%) who said they had not recently travelled out of town.

Table I: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population

Variables	Modalities	Frequencies
sex	Men	65 ; 65%
	Women	35 ; 35%
	Total	100 ; 100%
residential area	Jamboutou	42 ; 42,0%
	Yelwa	32 ; 32,0%
	Rounde	26 ; 26,0%
	Total	100, 100%
marital status	Single	45 ; 45,0%
	Married	34 ; 34,0%
	As a couple	21 ; 21,0%
	Total	100 ; 100%
Profession	professional administrative staff	23;23%
	health pupils/students	9;9%
	man in suit	37;37%
	other	6;6%
	other	25;25%
	Total	100 ; 100%
knowledge of the virus	no	97 ; 97,0%
	yes	3 ; 3,0%
	Total	100 ; 100%
knowledge of vectors	yes	74 ; 74,0%
	no	26 ; 26,0%
	Total	100 ; 100%
sting frequency per mosquito	constantly	56 ; 56,6%
	often	34 ; 34,3%

	rarely	6 ; 6,1%
	never	3 ; 3,0%
	total	99
moment of sting	at night	56 ; 57,1%
	day and night	29 ; 29,6%
	the day	13 ; 13,3%
	total	100 ; 100%
suggestible elements	Puddle	69 ; 69,0%
	Can	48 ; 48,0%
	old tire	48 ; 48,0%
	car body	31 ; 31,0%
	tanker	23 ; 23,0%
	plant pot	20 ; 20,0%
	Total	100 ; 100%
insecticide	no	58 ; 58%
	yes	42 ; 42%
	Total	100 ; 100%
repulsifs	no	98 ; 98,0%
	YES	2 ; 2,0 %
	Total	100 ; 100%
Mosquitoes	YES	59 ; 59%
	NO	41 ; 41%
	Total	100 ; 100%
Origin of water consumption	Drilling	60 ; 60%
	pump	28 ; 28,%
	Well	9 ; 9%
	Lake	3 ; 3,0%
	river	0 ; 0,0%
Total	100; 100%	
Recent travel	YES	34 ; 34%
	NO	66 ; 66%
	Total	100 ; 100%

Population seroprevalence analysis

Table II shows the overall seroprevalence of Zika in the study population. The table shows that no cases of Zika were detected among the 100 individuals diagnosed.

Table II: Zika seroprevalence in the study population

Test	Positive	Negative	Total
Zika IgM	0	100	0
Zika IgG	0	100	0
Zika IgM/IgG	0	100	0
Zika NS1	0	100	0

Vector distribution

Figure 3 below shows the distribution of potential Zika virus vectors in the different study areas in Garoua. Data from positive sites for potential vectors were geo-referenced and illustrated using GPS. The various vectors were found in all three zones, with *Aedes Aegypti* numbering 136 more than *Aedes albopictus*, which numbered 36. The distribution of *Aedes aegypti* by zone shows a higher number of 47 in the Roumde zone than in the other zones, while the distribution of *Aedes albopictus* shows that it is the Jamboutou zone with a higher number of 21 than the Roumde and Yelwa zones.

Figure 3: Vector distribution map

Pre-imaginal infestation

A total of 301 potential breeding sites were surveyed, with 90 in the Jamboutou zone, 110 in the Roumde zone and 101 in the Yelwa zone. The sites surveyed contained larvae of various genera.

Figure 4: *Aedes aegypti* (a) *Aedes albopictus* collected (b)

Relationship between vector abundance and container type

Table III below shows the abundance of vectors collected according to the different areas surveyed. The table shows that potential vectors tend to colonize more peri-domestic containers, with a total of 87 *Aedes* collected, followed by natural containers, with 65 *Aedes* collected, and domestic containers, with 20 *Aedes* collected. The Roumde zone is the one with the highest number of vectors collected. *Aedes aegypti* is the vector with the highest numbers in the 03 zones.

Table III: Summary of vector abundance by type of deposit and surveyed area

	SELF-CATERING COTTAGES			PERIDOMESTIC GITES			NATURAL GITES			TOTAL	P VALUE	RR	CI
	pot of flower	Water tank	used tire	Car body	tank abandoned	Other	water stagnant	hole rock	Leaf				
YELWA ZONE													
<i>n Aedes aegypti</i>	1	3	5	2	6	3	11	8	2	41	1	1	,9451-2,345
<i>n Aedes albopictus</i>	0	1	1	0	1	1	4	1	0	9			
JAMBOUTOU ZONE													
<i>n Aedes aegypti</i>	2	4	2	2	11	8	8	0	1	38	0,3468	1,294	0,7820-2,386
<i>n Aedes albopictus</i>	1	1	2	1	1	9	3	2	1	21			
ROUMDE ZONE													
<i>n Aedes aegypti</i>	4	3	6	3	8	8	9	5	1	47	0,0404	1,73	1,021-3,216
<i>n Aedes albopictus</i>	0	0	2	1	1	3	9	0	0	16			
TOTAL	20			87			65			172			

RR = Relative Risk; n *Aedes aegypti*= number of *Aedes aegypti*; CI: Confidence Interval; P=Probability; n *Aedes albopictus*= number of *Aedes albopictus*

then illustrated vector density according to type of container for the 03 zones studied. This showed that the number of adult vectors derived from the larvae of the vectors collected was higher for *Aedes aegypti* in peridomestic containers in the Jamboutou and Roumde zones than in the Yelwa zone, where natural containers were the most heavily colonized larval habitats, whereas *Aedes albopictus* colonized natural containers in the Jamboutou and Yelwa zones. Graph 4 summarizes the number of vectors harvested by type of container

Figure 5: Vector abundance by container type

We carried out an ANOVA for *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* for the container types, and the probability value P gives us 0.0148 and 0.027 respectively, which are less than 0.05 at the 95% confidence interval: there is therefore a significant difference between the means of *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* from one container type to the other.

Infestation indicators

Table IV below summarizes the calculation of infestation indices as a function of building density. Specific infestation indices were calculated separately for each species. After comparing the different indices, those for *Aedes aegypti* were higher than those for *Aedes albopictus* in the 03 study areas.

Table IV: Summary of the calculation of infestation indices as a function of building density

Building density	Type of <i>Aedes</i>	Indices house	In-Breteau clues	Container indexes	Larval indicators
YELWA	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	27,27	29,09	20	16
*** n=55	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	12,72	12,72	5,45	5
** n=35	<i>Aedes Aegypti</i>	25,71	28,57	22,85	14

	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	2,85	2,85	2,85	1
*					
n=11	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	36,36	36,36	18,18	11
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	18,18	27,27	9,09	3
TOTAL	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	27,72	28,71	20,79	41
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i> <i>Aedes</i>	9,90	10,80	4,95	9
	<i>aegypti/Aedes</i>				
	<i>albopictus</i>	37,62	39,60	25,74	50
JAMBOUTOU					
	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	22,22	28,88	20	18
***	n=45				
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	17,77	20	13,33	11
**	n=35				
	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	22,85	25,71	17,14	15
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	14,28	17,14	8,57	6
*					
n=10	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	30	36,36	20	5
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	30	30	10	4
TOTAL	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	23,33	37,14	18,88	38
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i> <i>Aedes</i>	18,88	14,28	11,11	21
	<i>aegypti/Aedes</i>				
	<i>albopictus</i>	42,22	51,42	30	59
ROUMDE					
***	n=60				
	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	21,66	23,33	20	21
	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	6,66	10	5	8
**	n=35				
	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	14,28	20	17,14	10

	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	5,71	8,57	5,71	5
*	<i>Aedes aegypti</i>	26,66	26,66	27,27	16
n=15					

n=number of sites surveyed; ***=high building density; **=medium building density; *=low building density

Analysis after Table IV shows that :

In the Yelwa area, 101 potential breeding sites were surveyed, and 27 (26.73%) contained immature stages. Both species were inventoried and specific indices established. Overall infestation indices were 37.62 (IM), 39.60 (IB), 25.74 (IR) and 50 (IL). All indices were higher for *Aedes aegypti*. Indices are particularly high in areas of low building density. The house index is 37.62% > 0.05, so the risk of virus transmission by *Aedes aegypti* would be high in this area. Although the Breteau index is below 50 in this area, it is nevertheless a risk to be considered, especially in areas with low building density. In the Jamboutou region, 90 potential sites were inspected and 27 (30%) contained immature stages. We recovered both species in this area. Calculation of the infestation indices for the two species gives us 42.22%, 51.42%, 30% and 59 respectively for the House index, Breteau index, container index and larval index. The MI is greater than 5%, meaning that the risk of disease transmission is high even in areas with low building density. It is higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*, with a value of 23.33% versus 18.88%. The Breteau index value is over 50 in this area, so the risk of virus transmission would be very high. *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes have a higher IB of 37.14 compared with 14.28 for *Aedes albopictus*, indicating that the virus is more likely to be transmitted by *Aedes aegypti*. The container index for both species combined is average, but higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*. The larval index is higher in areas of high building density, and is greater for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*. In the Roumde area, 110 potential sites were surveyed and 26 (23.63%) were positive (containing immature stages of potential vectors). Cumulative vector indices give us 26.36%, 31.81%, 8.57% and 63 respectively for the House index, Breteau index, container index and larval index. All these indices are higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*. The MI is greater in low-density areas for *Aedes aegypti*, but its value in this zone is equal to that in high-density areas for *Aedes albopictus*. Its value is greater than 0.05, which is a risk for the population. Areas with low building density have a higher Breteau index for *Aedes aegypti*, whereas this index is higher in high-density areas for *Aedes albopictus*. The container index for both species combined is higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*, indicating that potential breeding sites contain more *Aedes aegypti* than *Aedes albopictus*. On the other hand, in the Roumde area, the larval index was higher for both species at high-density sites.

Discussion

The Zika virus represents a threat to public health in Cameroon. In this study, serological analysis was performed on 100 participants and we found 0% cases of Zika in the city of Garoua. The results of this study do not corroborate work that reported a seroprevalence of 4.8% among 186 blood donors in the city of Garoua on the potential introduction and subsequent spread to African urban areas of Zika currently circulating in the Americas and adapted to transmission by peridomestic mosquitoes [11]. Furthermore, both *Aedes* species were found in the city of Garoua, in contrast to studies that found only one species (*Aedes aegypti*) in the northern region and suggested that the northern limit of *Aedes albopictus* was 6°N [20] [22]. As regards the seroprevalence study, out of 100 samples collected, we did not diagnose any positive cases of Zika virus. The difference between this study and the previous one can be explained by the very small sample size. The sample size of the previous study was larger (186) than the current one [11]. The absence of positive cases in this study does not mean that the virus is not circulating in the city, but means that the virus is circulating but weakly in the population. The population is therefore immunologically naïve, they do not present antigens (NS1) and antibodies that react to the presence of the virus to fight it (IgG, IgM). Consequently, there is a risk of the virus spreading due to the presence of vectors and the potential introduction of the Asian genotype into the city, which could lead to an

epidemic [11]. In Garoua, two potential vectors have been identified: *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. *Aedes albopictus* is capable of colonizing a wide range of sites, from natural sites (tree hollows, bamboo and rocks, etc.) to artificial sites such as tires and small containers, both in its native region and in the invaded area ; and adapts according to the environment in which it is found. *Aedes albopictus*, once absent from Garoua, is currently invading the city. Its expansion is largely due to: the importation of goods from infected areas (tires, second-hand vehicles, etc.); international transport, with road traffic (Garoua-Chad section; Garoua-Nigeria; Garoua-Centrafrigue), air traffic (presence of an international airport) and sea traffic (presence of a river port). A recent study carried out in Nigeria revealed a prevalence of 19.2% in 03 hospitals in the country, the result of international trade in tires in particular. This finding should attract even more attention, as tires constitute an attractive oviposition site for *Aedes albopictus* females. Eggs laid on tire walls remain in a quiescent state during dry periods and last for varying lengths of time, so they can easily withstand travel from one country to another. This polytypy of colonized sites is also incriminated in the expansion of the species [23]. Although the results demonstrate the presence of *Aedes albopictus* in Garoua, the environment and climate appear to be unfavourable to the species, hence its low numbers compared with *Aedes aegypti*, as suggested by previous studies [19] [20]. In all regions of the world where these 02 species have been encountered, epidemics have followed [24]. This finding is consistent with previous studies on Zika prevalence and vector distribution in Cameroon [25] [11] Zika prevalence was highest where potential vectors were most abundant. These highly competent vectors have been implicated in several epidemics around the world, notably on the island of Yap [26], in Brazil [27], in French Polynesia [28] [29], in Mali. In Cameroon, initial studies had shown that *Aedes albopictus* was limited to the gateways, namely the coast, the South and the Centre [19] and that there was no vector in the city of Garoua. With urbanization, the city of Garoua is also being invaded by this vector, which amplifies the risk of an epidemic occurring due to the presence of two potential vectors. Although we didn't find any cases, the previous study suggests that this may be due to the low numbers of *Aedes albopictus* in this region, and that a larger study could lead to a better finding. To understand the ecology and distribution of potential Zika virus vectors, we calculated infestation indices in three areas. Overall, the results showed that all indices were higher for *Aedes aegypti*. We noted that *Aedes aegypti* is more abundant in areas with high building density, as suggested by previous studies [28]. This observation can be explained by the fact that areas with high construction density have many resources and oviposition sites. In the Yelwa zone, the House index is over 5%, so the risk of virus transmission would be high in this area. Although the Breteau index is below 50 in this area, it is nevertheless a risk to be considered, especially in areas with low building density [10]. In the Jamboutou Zone, the calculation of infestation indices gives us for both species 42.22%, 51.42%, 30% and 59 respectively for the House index, Breteau index, container index and larval index. The MI is greater than 5%, meaning that the risk of disease transmission is high even in areas with low building density. It is higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*, with a value of 23.33% versus 18.88%. The Breteau index value is over 50 in this area, so the risk of virus transmission would be very high. *Ae. aegypti* mosquitoes have a higher IB of 37.14 versus 14.28 for *Ae. albopictus*, indicating that the virus is more likely to be transmitted by *Ae. aegypti*. The container index for the two species combined is not very high, but it is higher for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*. The larval index is higher in areas of high building density and is greater for *Aedes aegypti* than for *Aedes albopictus*, as the latter like to be close to habitats for feeding [20]

The Roudé zone is the one in which we recorded the highest number of larvae (63). This means that the population in this zone is at high risk of infestation. All indices in this zone are higher for both species. This is due to the fact that the genus *Aedes* has a wide worldwide distribution, adapting easily to the environment in which it is found [30]. The MI is greater in low-density areas for *Aedes aegypti*, but its value in this area is equal to that in high-density areas for *Aedes albopictus*. This result can be justified as its value is greater than 0.05, which is a risk for the resident population in this zone. When we compared vector abundance according to container type, we found a significant difference between *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* container types. We found a significant difference between *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* container types ($P=0.0148$). The number of adult vector larvae collected was significantly higher in peridomestic containers ($P=0.027$) in the Jamboutou and Roudé zones. In fact, domestic containers are constantly cleaned, so larvae are less likely to be present, whereas containers abandoned in the peri-domestic environment and filled with rainwater are the main colonization sites for potential vectors [10]. These results corroborate work which suggested that these vectors thrive best in peri-domestic environments. In the Yelwa area, in contrast to the two study areas, natural containers were found to be the most heavily colonized larval habitats. Peri-domestic containers were in very short supply in the surveyed area, which pushed vectors to reproduce in natural containers in greater numbers, although socio-anthropological studies on the use and management of these reservoirs are needed to confirm this observation [20].

Study limits

The limitations of our study are the sample size, which is very small due to the lack of financial means to purchase a large number of reagents to analyze a large number of samples. Secondly, time did not allow us to collect a large number of samples.

Conclusion

The Zika virus is a real health problem worldwide. Due to the presence of its vectors *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*, a study of the prevalence of the virus was necessary. Our study did not enable us to show the circulation of the virus, as no cases were diagnosed positive, due to the small sample size. However, the study did reveal the presence of the second potential vector, *Aedes albopictus*, which was not initially present in Garoua. Given this finding, we believe that the absence or low level of antibodies is a factor favoring the occurrence of an epidemic, given that Garoua is a cosmopolitan city, open to the world, where cases of Zika can be imported, hence the need to set up surveillance of this virus which causes so much damage and complications.

Outlook

It is undeniable that the risk of Zikv transmission is very real in Garoua due to the presence of its possible vectors *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. We therefore recommend : Carry out a large-scale study with a subsequent sample to determine whether or not the virus is circulating in the city of Garoua, carry out a spatial study in dry and wet periods to decipher the behavior of the vectors studied, and carry out associated molecular analyses that could give more value to the results we find.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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